

Grant Agreement No. 101131826

CoARA Boost

2nd Cascade Funding Competitive Call Text and Guidelines for Applicants

Deliverable 5.5.

CoARA Boost:

D.5.5. 2nd Cascade Funding Competitive Call Text and Guidelines for Applicants

Table of Contents

Document information	3
Document History.....	4
List of Acronyms	4
List of Figures	4
Executive Summary.....	5
Project Summary	6
1. Purpose and Scope of the Deliverable	8
2. Call Text Document	9
3. Guideline for Applicants.....	22
4. Conclusion	42

Document information

Project	
Project Name	Strengthening CoARA and Enabling Systemic Reform of Research Assessment - A Booster
Project Acronym	CoARA Boost
Call	HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01
Topic	HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-07
Project Starting Date	01-10-2023
Project Duration	36 months

Deliverable	
Deliverable number	D.5.5
Deliverable title	2nd Cascade Funding Competitive Call Text and Guidelines for Applicants
Deliverable version	1.1
Work Package number	5
Work Package Title	Catalysing change: CoARA Boost Cascade Funding Programme
Responsible Partner	ESF
Due Date of Delivery	31 - 12 - 2024
Dissemination Level	PU (Public)
Type	R (Document, Report)
Author(s)	Damini PANTALEON, ESF
Contributor(s)	N/A
Reviewer(s)	Erzsébet TOTH-CZIFRA, ESF
Rights	Creative Commons 3.0

Document History

Version	Date	Partner	Description
1.0	21 – 02 – 2025	ESF	First draft
1.1.	11 – 03 – 2025	ESF	Final version

List of Acronyms

Acronym	Abbreviations
ARRA	Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment
CET	Central European Time
CEST	Central European Summer Time
CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
D.X.X	Deliverable X.X.
ERA	European Research Area
ESF	European Science Foundation
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
K EUR/€	Kilo euros
M EUR/€	Million euros
MY Y	Month YY
TPPA	Third-Party Project Agreement
P01/P02/P03	Project 01/02/03
PU	Public
R	Report

List of Figures

Not applicable.

PART 1: CONTEXTUAL INFORMATION

Executive Summary

The CoARA Boost Cascade Funding programme forms a central component of the CoARA Boost project. It represents more than half of the project's overall budget. It aims to facilitate institutional change and support the implementation of the CoARA Agreement in a broad diversity of contexts.

The programme will support a minimum of 50 organisations in tackling specific challenges related to reforming research assessment. By supporting different types of proposals, the programme maintains a balanced portfolio of projects. The cascade funding programme consists of two rounds of open calls, the first one launched in April 2024 and second one in February 2025.

As such, it encourages and supports research organisations to investigate and test what will efficiently work 'in real life'.

Deliverable 5.5., contains the call text and guidelines for applicants as defined for the second round of the call. It has been published on the 21st of February 2025, followed by a consultation with the CoARA Steering Board, the CoARA Boost consortium as well as with relevant departments of the European Commission.

Project Summary

Over 800 research organisations, funders, assessment authorities, professional societies, and their associations have agreed on a common direction and principles for reforming the assessment of research, researchers and research organisations, outlined in the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment. They have also committed to implement changes within their organisations.

The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment, CoARA, offers a platform for collaboration and mutual learning. However, given the complexity of the reform process, providing support for institutions to test, design, and carry out in-depth institutional changes is crucial to implement the Agreement commitments.

The CoARA Boost project, funded by the European Union, strengthens CoARA's operational capacity. It provides a means to develop a critical mass for reforming research assessment, to generate gravitas for new members as well as to investigate and implement new models for research assessment. CoARA Boost i) strengthens CoARA's operational capacity, ii) catalyses knowledge development, policy evolution, and institutional change in research assessment, iii) facilitates the collection and exchange of information, and iv) widens the coalition's membership in Europe and beyond. The project is crucial for the global growth of the reform-focused community, amplifying collaboration and enhancing knowledge exchange and mutual learning within the coalition.

Main actions carried out by the CoARA Boost project include:

- Expanding the operational support to the coalition, including enabling multiple approaches of knowledge sharing among the coalition members.
- Supporting signatories in compiling and executing on their action plans towards the achievement of the agreed 10 commitments. As well as based on the action plans establishing an observatory of responsible research assessment practices reaching well beyond the realm of European stakeholders.
- Providing operational assistance to Working Groups in their exploration of new models of research assessment.
- Catalysing change via the CoARA Boost cascade funding program that will be facilitating institutional reform pathways to a significant number of organisations of different types and across geographical areas as well

as solutions and resources that members of the coalition can rely on in their efforts in implementing core commitments of CoARA.

- Expanding the outreach of European efforts to reform research assessment by growing the membership of CoARA globally and fostering international cooperation on evolutions in research assessment.

1. Purpose and Scope of the Deliverable

The document is based on the terms and conditions established in the Grant Agreement no. 101131826 signed on the 30th of October 2023 and its Annexes, amended on the 20th of February 2025, as well as in the Consortium Agreement signed by all project partners on the 29th of October 2023.

The deliverable aims to provide a comprehensive overview of documents made available to Call 2 of the Cascade Funding applicants, implemented within WP5 “Catalysing change: CoARA Boost Cascade Funding programme”.

PART 2: Call and Guidelines of Cascade Funding Call 2

The aim of this deliverable is to provide the content of the 2nd Cascade Funding and especially the call text laying down the expectations and conditions of the call and the Guideline developed for the applicants.

2. Call Text Document

The “Call Text” – available for applicants via the CoARA website, the European Commission’s Funding and Tender Portal as well as on the SmartSimple submission platform – is presented below

Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment

CoARA Boost Cascade Funding Programme

Call Text – Second Round

Opening: 21 February 2025

Closing: 23 April 2025 at 17:00 CEST

Funding Call information, documents and templates:

<https://coara.eu/second-call-for-cascade-funding/>

Funding Call Application Platform:

https://esf.smartsimple.ie/s_signup.jsp?token=XVtQC1oGYV5ZSxtZXxJXR1JWYUIIH3Rt

CoARA Boost Cascade Funding Call Text – second round

Contents

Contents	11
1. Key figures	12
2. Context of the call	12
3. Summary of the call	13
4. Eligibility criteria	14
5. Cost eligibility	15
6. Scope	15
7. Types of projects	15
Teaming projects	16
Institutional pilot projects	16
Institutional change projects	17
8. Evaluation process	18
Contact information	20
Feedback to applicants	21
9. Application Form	21

Key figures

Available funding	Up to 1.22 M €
Funding per project	30,000 EUR to 60,000 EUR: a lump sum, depending on the type of project
Number of projects to be funded	20–25 projects
Target applicants	Legal entities interested in reforming research assessment practices in their institutions
2nd call opens	21 February 2025 – 23 April 2025
Duration of the projects	Implementation within 12 months after signature of a Third-Party Project Agreement – TPPA
Start of the projects	Within 1 month from TPPA signature

Context of the call

Over 800 research organisations, funders, assessment authorities, professional societies, and their associations have agreed on a common direction and principles for reforming the assessment of research, researchers and research organisations, outlined in the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#). They have also committed to implement changes within their organisations.

The [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#), CoARA, offers a platform for collaboration and mutual learning. However, given the complexity of the reform process, **providing support for institutions to test, design, and carry out in-depth institutional changes** is crucial to implement the Agreement commitments.

The CoARA Boost project, funded by the European Union, strengthens CoARA's operational capacity. It provides a means to develop a critical mass for reforming research assessment, to generate gravitas for new members as well as to investigate and implement new models for research assessment. Find out more about the project here: [CoARA Boost Project](#)

The Cascade Funding Programme within CoARA Boost represents more than half of the project's overall budget. This programme will support a minimum of 50

organisations in tackling specific challenges related to reforming research assessment and implementing the Agreement commitments. By supporting different types of proposals, the programme will maintain a balanced portfolio of projects. The cascade funding programme consists of two rounds of open calls, the first one was launched in April 2024 and second one in February 2025.

Summary of the call

CoARA Boost’s Cascade Funding calls facilitate institutional change and targets pilot and exchange-of-knowledge initiatives. It will fund +20 projects facilitating knowledge-exchange, piloting new initiatives within institutions, and enabling lasting institutional change. As such, it encourages and supports research organisations to investigate and test what will efficiently work ‘in real life’. More specifically, the Call aims to:

- Facilitate the exchange, transfer and adaptation of proven good practices and their adoption in research organisations.
- Catalyse the set-up or transformation of research assessment practices and tools in line with the commitments of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment.
- Support the development and testing of new and innovative research assessment approaches, models and procedures.

Projects can be proposed by any of the organisation types specified below through a cascading grant mechanism. By the end of the programme, it is expected to have a **diverse portfolio of projects available that will translate the shared vision outlined in the Agreement into tangible, lasting institutional changes in research assessment practices.**

Eligibility criteria

The primary targets of the CoARA Boost Cascade Funding Programme are legal entities of the following types:

- Academies, learned societies that implement some form of research assessment;
- National/regional authorities or agencies that implement some form of research assessment;
- Public or private research funding organisations;
- Research centres, research infrastructures;
- Universities;
- Other relevant non-for-profit organisations that implement some form of research assessment.

Applications from faculties of universities are also eligible. However, the application needs to be formally in the name of the university (applicant), and not the faculty.

As the call is meant to support institutions from across the European Research Area (ERA), only legal entities based in the EU Member States and [countries associated to the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation](#) (see under the heading “Third countries associated to Horizon Europe”) are eligible to apply.

The proposal is submitted by a designated point of contact authorised to do so on behalf of the organisation they are affiliated with.

A maximum of one application per organisation is allowed for all calls.

Consortium members of the CoARA Boost project are not eligible to participate in the call. In the case of beneficiaries that are umbrella organisations, their member organisations are eligible. Nominating organisations of the CoARA Steering Board members are also eligible, as the Steering Board does not directly participate in the evaluation of the proposals. The Steering Board will not have any role in both the evaluation and selection of winning applications.

To ensure diversity in the allocation of resources, [beneficiaries of the first round of the CoARA Boost Cascade Funding](#) are not eligible to apply.

Cost eligibility

Cascade Funding will be aimed at covering costs that are exclusively considered eligible by the provisions of the WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-07 call.

Further eligibility details can be found as part of the [FAQs](#).

Scope

The total budget for the call is up to 2.33 M€, of which 1.12 M€ has been released for the first round and up to 1.22 M € are released in the second round.

Proposals may be funded up to 30.000–60.000 € each (including indirect costs, see specified below per cost).

25 projects were selected and funded within the first round:

- 3 Teaming Projects,
- 13 Institutional Pilot Projects,
- 9 Institutional Change Projects.

Except for the teaming projects (see below), the cascade funding program is designed for mono beneficiaries (i.e., one organization per application).

In the case of teaming calls, co-applications from max. 3 organisations are welcome. There are no restrictions in place regarding the type or country/countries of these organisations, apart from the basic eligibility criteria specified above.

Types of projects

The CoARA Boost cascading grants are a tool for organisations to implement the 10 commitments that are enshrined in the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) (ARRA) and facilitate institutional change in the context of research assessment. The activities eligible for support must demonstrate the commitment to a systemic change with medium-term or long-term trajectories and impact. The grants will support organisations to develop, pilot and implement, assessment criteria, tools and processes; while avoiding contradictions across assessment systems, types and purposes, through continuous dialogue. There is room for diverse starting points and approaches. As part of the Call, three types of projects will be supported. These reflect different stages of an institution's reform journey, namely:

1. knowledge exchange (teaming projects),
2. piloting (institutional pilot projects),

3. paving the way for a lasting change (institutional change projects).

Their description is provided below.

Teaming projects

Organisations are encouraged to share practices and experiences to foster mutual learning and ensure continuous mutual improvement, while respecting organisations' autonomy. Teaming projects **facilitate the transfer and adaptation of experience and practices from a more advanced/experienced organisation to one or more less experienced ones**. In addition to knowledge transfer between institutions of the same type, co-piloting innovations across different types of organisations, such as universities and national evaluation agencies or academies and open infrastructure providers, are also welcome to co-apply as a team.

Examples of activities

Projects could involve transferring or benefitting from existing knowledge, testing the feasibility of adapting and implementing solutions that work in another institutional context, enhancing capacity-building or enhancing open infrastructural components of responsible research assessment. These projects could allow the organisation of demonstration sessions, seminars, training as well as short visits. Other examples include the review, transfer and adaptation of documents, procedures and workflows.

These examples of activities are provided as a source of inspiration: innovative ideas are welcome.

Maximum grant amount: 40 K€ (in total for all the organisations taking part in the teaming project)

Maximum project duration: 1 year

Institutional pilot projects

Institutional pilot projects offer an opportunity for institutions **to experiment with and evaluate new assessment approaches, procedures, frameworks, and tools in the context of a clearly defined initiative** (such as a pilot competitive call in a university or the development of a concept). These projects help institutions develop, pilot, and implement assessment criteria, tools and processes while ensuring consistency

across assessment systems, types and purposes. While the institutional change projects will address issues that are relevant for the entire institution's assessment mechanisms and pave the way towards lasting change, institutional pilot projects target a specific action and should allow grantees to explore new modes of operation. Applications for pilot projects at the level of faculties are eligible if the application is submitted by their institution.

Examples of activities

As institutional pilot projects should respond to specific needs within the organisation, the types of funded activities will vary from one project to another. As an example, they could involve the following: development and deployment of (IT-based) workflows, adoption of qualitative KPIs, adoption of open infrastructure, bringing more diversity to the assessment of research outputs and academic activities, balancing quantitative and qualitative criteria, training, implementing practical ways of recognising diverse research contributions, core narrative CV with different disciplinary expectations, more credit given to research project proposals whether successful or not, more credit for outreach activities, crediting societal impact and knowledge valorisation, valuing institutions contributing to move away from rankings and impact factors i.e. more responsible use of metrics, present alternatives in terms of data used to assess research groups and institutions, integration of Open Science, research data sharing contributions into research(er) assessment, simplifying research evaluation systems of increasing their flexibility etc.

Applicants are also encouraged to gain inspiration from 'Annex 4: Toolbox: practical tools and options to consider' of the [Agreement](#). Projects could involve piloting the implementation of the [SCOPE](#) framework within their organisation or testing and implementing practical solutions, such as recommendations, guidelines and tools developed by CoARA Working Groups.

Maximum grant amount: 30 K€

Maximum project duration: 1 year

Institutional change projects

Institutional change projects **provide the means to accelerate change in procedures and process in an organisation**. These projects should enable a review of internal assessment processes within the awarded organisation, aiming to align them more closely with the Agreement's

commitments. If the granted organisation does not have a (well-developed) assessment structure, these projects should allow to set up such structures.

Examples of activities

As for the pilot projects above, institutional change projects should respond to specific needs within the organisation and the types of activities funded will vary from one project to another.

All the activities listed under the "Institutional pilot projects" section are welcome, except on a different maturity level and possibly on a different scale. While institutional pilot projects are designed to explore the feasibility and test innovations associated with the reform of research assessment within an organisation, institutional change calls are instruments to sustainably integrate such changes in the applicant organisation's institutional policies and practices and thus to make a lasting change. Institutional change calls are recommended to organisations who already have a reform policy in place but need resources for implementing certain elements of it or invest in more thorough reflections, consultation, documentation and knowledge sharing within and possibly beyond the scope of the applicant organisation (for instance, to CoARA members). In this case, the added value of the project is to be clearly indicated in the work plan to avoid funding projects that would happen to be implemented anyway.

Maximum grant amount: 60 K€

Maximum project duration: 1 year

Evaluation process

All applications will be assessed by a review panel composed of experts in research assessment, set up by the CoARA Secretariat/European Science Foundation (ESF). Reviewers are selected from the contact database of CoARA, from the contact database associated with CoARA's collaboration history with experts and expert groups in research assessment as well as from a pool referrals from the CoARA Boost consortium and the Steering Board. In addition to relevance of topical expertise, the CoARA Secretariat will also adhere to diversity measures in terms of geographical coverage (balanced representation of all European regions at least 5% of the reviewers outside of Europe), type of institution in affiliation (proportionate to CoARA membership), gender (no more than 2/3 of the pool of selected reviewers should represent the same gender) and career stage (at least 25% of the pool of selected reviewers should be early career researchers). The review panels will assess applications submitted to the type of project that fall within their policy and/or research expertise. Each submission will be pre-assessed by 2 panel

members: one Lead Reviewer panellist and one Secondary Reviewer panellist who will provide written pre-assessments of each application. The Lead Reviewer panellist will present these pre-assessments when introducing the application during the panel. For equal treatment of applications, all panel members will be asked to read all proposals belonging to their panel prior to the panel discussions.

Following the three themes of the call specified in the call for proposals, one topical panel will be dedicated to each, namely:

P01 – Teaming projects

P02 – Institutional change project

P03 – Institutional pilot projects.

The evaluation procedure consists of the following stages:

Phase	Process	Timeline
Formal eligibility check	Performed by the CoARA Secretariat	End of April 2025
Pre-assessment	<p>All applications will be made available to the review panel prior to the panel meetings.</p> <p>Each application will be pre-assessed by one Lead Reviewer panellist and one Secondary Reviewer panellist. They will have access to each other's reviews.</p> <p>For equal treatment of applications, all panel members will be asked to read all proposals belonging to their panel prior to the panel discussions.</p>	May 2025
Review panels	<p>During the review panel meetings (teleconference), each application will be presented by their reviewers and discussed by the full panel.</p> <p>Each application will be presented</p>	June 2025

	<p>by Lead Reviewer panellists who will introduce both pre-assessments alongside the application.</p> <p>The review panel will then agree on an overall mark for each application and produce a ranked list of applications.</p>	
Panel chairs' meeting	<p>During the panel chairs meeting (teleconference), chairs of the topical panels bring results of their respective topical panels together. They agree on the overall ranking (i.e. rankings from each panel) and make final selection decisions.</p>	End of June 2025
Panel meeting outcomes – consensus reports	<p>The panel members will then produce a consensus report for each application, summarising the panel discussions. Narrative comments (not scores) from the consensus reports will be communicated to the applicants.</p>	<p>Mid-July 2025</p> <p>Project start: 1st of September 2025</p>

Further information on diversity measures when compiling the pool of reviewers as well as a detailed description of the evaluation process can be found in document 2: EVALUATION GUIDELINES.

Contact information

Any questions regarding the call can be directed to the CoARA Secretariat: funding@coara.org

In case of technical questions concerning the submission platform SmartSimple (operated by [ESF](#)) please reach out to: esf-panels@esf.org

An online information session for interested parties has been organised on the 30 of January 2025 at 14:00 CET, the materials presented during the session are available here: <https://zenodo.org/records/14794738>.

Feedback to applicants

All applicants submitting a Cascade Funding Project proposal will be informed of the outcome of the selection process by mid-July 2025. A brief evaluation report with narrative comments from the panel consensus reports will be provided.

Application Form

1. The first part of the application form should be completed directly on the SmartSimple platform. For technical guidelines on the Platform, please refer to Document 3 Guidelines for Applicants.
2. The second part of the application form must be uploaded on the SmartSimple platform. The Application Template can be downloaded from the [webpage of the Call](#): Annex 2_Application Template and Annex_4 and Annex_5 Project Budget.

The use of the Application Template and Use of Resources Templates are mandatory – please refrain from deleting any sections and adhere to the specified page limit (please do not exceed 5 pages, all included, i.e., figures, tables, charts, etc.) – font-size Arial 11. These forms must be entirely filled and uploaded on the online SmartSimple platform in PDF format as specified on the application platform.

3. Guideline for Applicants

The “Guidelines for Applicants” – available for applicants via the CoARA website, the European Commission’s Funding and Tender Portal as well as on the SmartSimple submission platform – is presented below

Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment

CoARA Boost Cascade Funding Programme

Guidelines for Applicants – Second Round

Opening: 21 February 2025

Closing: 23 April 2025 at 17:00 CEST

Funding Call information, documents and templates:

<https://coara.eu/second-call-for-cascade-funding/>

Funding Call Application Platform:

https://esf.smartsimple.ie/s_signup.jsp?token=XVtQC1oGYV5ZSxtZXxJXR1JWYUIIH3Rt

Contents

Introduction	25
Key figures	25
Context of the call	25
Summary of the call	26
Types of projects	26
Relevant dates	27
Applications	27
Rules and conditions	27
Eligible countries	27
Eligible beneficiaries	27
Financial Support	28
Subcontracting	28
Indicative distribution of the funds	29
Origin of the funds	29
Evaluation Procedure	29
Evaluation Criteria	30
Submission Requirements	31
Overall process	31
Application reception	34
Language	34
Ethical Issues	34
Data Protection	34
Contact information	35
Support information	35
Technical Guidelines – Platform Guidelines for Applicants	36
REGISTER	36
LOG IN TO THE PLATFORM	38
SUBMIT YOUR APPLICATION	39

Introduction

This document aims to assist applicants submitting proposals for the second Cascade Funding Call under CoARA Boost. It contains information on eligibility criteria, evaluation procedure, submission requirements and timeline for the call.

Key figures

Total funding	Up to 1.22 M €
Funding per project	30,000 EUR to 60,000 EUR: a lump sum, depending on the type of project
Number of projects to be funded	20-25 projects
Target applicants	Legal entities interested in reforming research assessment practices in their institutions
2nd call opens	21 February 2025 – 23 April 2025
Duration of the projects	Implementation within 12 months after signature of a Third-Party Project Agreement – TPPA
Start of the projects	Within 1 month from TPPA signature

Context of the call

Over 800 research organisations, funders, assessment authorities, professional societies, and their associations have agreed on a common direction and principles for reforming the assessment of research, researchers and research organisations, outlined in the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#). They have also committed to implement changes within their organisations.

The [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment](#), CoARA, offers a platform for collaboration and mutual learning. However, given the complexity of the reform process, **providing support for institutions to test, design, and carry out in-depth institutional changes** is crucial to implement the Agreement commitments.

The CoARA Boost project, funded by the European Union, strengthens CoARA's operational capacity. It provides a means to develop a critical mass for reforming

research assessment, to generate gravitas for new members as well as to investigate and implement new models for research assessment. Find out more about the project here: [CoARA Boost Project](#)

The Cascade Funding Programme within CoARA Boost represents more than half of the project's overall budget. This programme will support a minimum of 50 organisations in tackling specific challenges related to reforming research assessment and implementing the Agreement commitments. By supporting different types of proposals, the programme will maintain a balanced portfolio of projects. The cascade funding programme consists of two rounds of open calls, the first one was launched in April 2024 and second one in February 2025.

Summary of the call

CoARA Boost's Cascade Funding calls facilitate institutional change and targets pilot and exchange-of-knowledge initiatives. It will fund +20 projects facilitating knowledge-exchange, piloting new initiatives within institutions, and enabling lasting institutional change. As such, it encourages and supports research organisations to investigate and test what will efficiently work 'in real life'. More specifically, the Call aims to:

- Facilitate the exchange, transfer and adaptation of proven good practices and their adoption in research organisations.
- Catalyse the set-up or transformation of research assessment practices and tools in line with the commitments of the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment.
- Support the development and testing of new and innovative research assessment approaches, models and procedures.

Projects can be proposed by any of the organisation types specified below through a cascading grant mechanism. By the end of the programme, it is expected to have a **diverse portfolio of projects available that will translate the shared vision outlined in the Agreement into tangible, lasting institutional changes in research assessment practices.**

Types of projects

The CoARA Boost cascading grants are a tool for organisations to implement the 10 commitments that are enshrined in the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) (ARRA) and facilitate institutional change in the context of research assessment. The activities eligible for support must demonstrate the commitment to a systemic change with medium-term or long-term trajectories and impact. The

grants will support organisations to develop, pilot and implement, assessment criteria, tools and processes; while avoiding contradictions across assessment systems, types and purposes, through continuous dialogue. There is room for diverse starting points and approaches. As part of the first call, three types of projects will be supported. These reflect different stages of an institution's reform journey, namely: 1. knowledge exchange (teaming projects), 2. piloting (institutional pilot projects), 3. paving the way for a lasting change (institutional change projects). Their description is provided in DOCUMENT 1.

Relevant dates

Applications

Opening: 21.02.2025

Deadline for submission: 21.04.2025, 17:00h CEST

Rules and conditions

Eligible countries

As the call is meant to support institutions from across the European Research Area (ERA), only legal entities based in the EU Member States and [countries associated to the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation](#) (see under the heading "Third countries associated to Horizon Europe") are eligible to apply.

For more details on eligibility details, please consult the [FAQ](#).

Eligible beneficiaries

The primary targets of the CoARA Boost Cascade Funding Programme are legal entities of the following types:

- Academies, learned societies that implement some form of research assessment,
- National/regional authorities or agencies that implement some form of research assessment,
- Public or private research funding organisations,
- Research centres, research infrastructures,
- Universities,
- Other relevant non-for-profit organisations that implement some form of research assessment.

Applications from faculties of universities are also eligible. However, the application needs to be formally in the name of the university (applicant), and not the faculty.

Consortium members of the CoARA Boost project are not eligible to participate in the call. In the case of beneficiaries that are umbrella organisations, their member organisations are eligible. Nominating organisations of the CoARA Steering Board members are also eligible, as the Steering Board does not directly participate in the evaluation of the proposals. The Steering Board will not have any role in both the evaluation and selection of winning applications.

To ensure diversity in the allocation of resources, [beneficiaries of the first round of the CoARA Boost Cascade Funding](#) are not eligible to apply.

Financial Support

CoARA Boost Cascade Funding will only provide financial support to entities (registered in Member States or associated countries) for the successful projects submitted to this open call.

The total budget available for this second call is 1.22M EUR. The grant is distributed over the course of the CoARA Boost project, following a "flat rate" approach. This means that the funding is distributed gradually, subject to meeting specific outcomes and milestones included in the agreement, considering completion of activities/tasks as indicator, but also taking into account administrative justifications of time and/or expenses claimed in the application.

The program offers three types of grants based on the project's type:

Types of projects	Maximum grant amount	Maximum project duration
1. Teaming projects	40 k€	1 year
2. Institutional pilot projects	30 k€	1 year
3. Institutional change projects	60 k€	1 year

Subcontracting

Regarding "subcontracting," it is important to note that within the context of CoARA Boost Cascade Funding, subcontracting is strictly prohibited for core/essential tasks. This signifies that the primary responsibilities associated with the project must be undertaken and carried out by the team members described in the proposal. It is essential to maintain a clear understanding that the core tasks

should not be delegated to external entities or subcontractors. The team should possess the necessary expertise and capacity to fulfil these crucial obligations to ensure the successful execution of the project.

Indicative distribution of the funds

Payments will be disbursed in two stages of meeting designated milestones or KPIs and delivering specific outputs, considering the work plan and resources claimed in the application.

- 70% once KPIs definition and outcomes are approved by the CoARA Secretariat (approx. month 1)
- 30% after the final review (approx. month 12, depending on the project duration)

Origin of the funds

Once an applicant has been selected for funding, they will be required to sign a dedicated Sub-Grantee Funding Agreement with the CoARA Boost Coordinator (ESF). It is important to note that the funds attached to the Sub-Grantee Funding Agreement come directly from the funds of the Horizon Europe Project CoARA Boost, which has been funded by the European Commission via Grant Agreement Number 101131826.

Evaluation Procedure

Formal eligibility check: Performed by CoARA Secretariat. **End of April 2025**

Pre-assessment: All applications will be made available to the review panel prior to the panel meetings, for each application to be pre-assessed by two panel members and read by all panel members. Each submission will be reviewed by one Lead Reviewer panellist and one Secondary Reviewer panellist. They will have access to each other's reviews. **May 2025**

Review panels: During the review panel meetings (teleconference), each application will be presented by their reviewers and discussed by the full panel. Each application will be presented by Lead Reviewer panellists who will introduce both pre-assessments alongside the application. At the end of each panel, recommendations for funding allocation ('to be funded', 'to be funded if funding available', 'not to be funded') will be collectively agreed by the panellists. **June 2025**

Panel chairs' meeting: During the panel chairs meeting (teleconference), chairs of the topical panels bring results of their respective topical panels together. They agree on the overall funding recommendations and make final selection decisions.

End of June 2025

Results: The panel members will then produce a consensus report for each application, summarising the panel discussions. Narrative assessment from the consensus reports will be communicated to the applicants, together with information on which evaluation brackets/quadrant the project fell into:

- To be funded with strong consensus
- To be funded – close to the cut-off line
- Not to be funded – close to the cut-off line
- Not to be funded.

Mid-July 2025

Further information on diversity measures when compiling the pool of reviewers as well as a detailed description of the evaluation process can be found in document 2: EVALUATION GUIDELINES.

Evaluation Criteria

Panellists will evaluate the proposals considering three criteria. Criteria will bear an equal weight in the assessment and each criterion will be qualitatively assessed following the scales provided in the table below. Scoring is complemented by comments from reviewers.

Reviewers will score each award criterion on a scale from 0 to 5:

Score	Definition
0	Proposal fails to address the criterion or cannot be assessed due to missing or incomplete information.
1	Poor – criterion is inadequately addressed or there are serious inherent weaknesses.
2	Fair – proposal broadly addresses the criterion, but there are significant weaknesses
3	Good – proposal addresses the criterion well, but a number of shortcomings are present.
4	Very good – proposal addresses the criterion very well, but a small number of shortcomings are present.
5	The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.

The total score will be calculated as the sum of the score of the three criteria. The threshold for each criterion will be three (3), while the overall score threshold will be ten (10). That means if a proposal receives less than 3 in one criterion or less than

10 overall score, will not be recommended for funding by the independent evaluators and will be automatically rejected.

The scoring sheet and detailed evaluation criteria can be found in Annex 3.

Submission Requirements

Overall process

The submission will be done through the official SmartSimple submission platform (operated by [ESF](#)), which is directly linked to the CoARA Boost Website at <https://coara.eu/call-cascade-funding-coara-boost/>. Only applications received directly through this platform will be considered eligible. For technical guidelines on how to use the platform, see the section “Technical Guidelines – Platform Guidelines for Applicants”.

The application form must be submitted in two steps:

3. The first part of the application form should be completed directly on the SmartSimple platforms. For technical guidelines on the Platform, please to “Technical Guidelines – Platform Guidelines for Applicants” final section of this document.

Title of the proposal *	
Type of project*	<p><i>Please select one among the following:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Teaming projects • Institutional change projects • Institutional pilot projects
Main keyword*:	<p><i>Please select one among the following:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Assessment of research organisations</i> • <i>Careers</i> • <i>Assessment of research proposals</i> • <i>Changing culture</i> • <i>CVs and Narrative</i> • <i>Disciplines and inter, trans and multidisciplinary</i> • <i>Diversity</i> • <i>Equity</i> • <i>Ethics and integrity</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Impact</i> • <i>Language</i> • <i>Metrics and indicators</i> • <i>Open Science</i> • <i>Peer-review</i> • <i>Quality and excellence</i> • <i>Raising awareness and engagement</i> • <i>Rankings</i> • <i>Sharing good practices</i> • <i>Sustainability (e.g. costs, over-assessment, reviewer fatigue)</i> • <i>Team science</i> • <i>Transparency</i> • <i>Other. please specify.</i>
<p>Second keyword (optional):</p>	<p><i>Please select up to two among the following:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Assessment of research organisations</i> • <i>Careers</i> • <i>Assessment of research proposals</i> • <i>Changing culture</i> • <i>CVs and Narrative</i> • <i>Disciplines and inter, trans and multidisciplinary</i> • <i>Diversity</i> • <i>Equity</i> • <i>Ethics and integrity</i> • <i>Impact</i> • <i>Language</i> • <i>Metrics and indicators</i> • <i>Open Science</i> • <i>Peer-review</i>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Quality and excellence</i> • <i>Raising awareness and engagement</i> • <i>Rankings</i> • <i>Sharing good practices</i> • <i>Sustainability (e.g. costs, over-assessment, reviewer fatigue)</i> • <i>Team science</i> • <i>Transparency</i> • <i>Other. please specify.</i>
Contact details of the project coordinator: *	Title, First and Last name, affiliation, department, e-mail address and ORCID ID
I confirm that I have the authority to submit the proposal on behalf of my organisation and on behalf of the organisations mentioned in point 7 below: *	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • No
Name and PIC number of the organisation*	

*Mandatory

- The second part of the application form must be uploaded on the SmartSimple platform. The Application Template can be downloaded from the [webpage of the Call](#): Annex 2_Application Template and Annex_4 and 5_Project Budget. The use of the Application Template and Use of Resources Templates are mandatory – please do not delete any sections and keep to the page limit (please do not exceed 5 pages, all included, i.e., figures, tables, charts, etc.) – font-size Arial 11.

These forms must be entirely filled and uploaded to the online SmartSimple platform. Applicants shall merge Application Template and Use of Resources Template before uploading them as one sign file PDF file as specified on the application platform.

Sending these templates in any other format and via e-mail or any other means will automatically disqualify the submission.

Application reception

Submissions will be done only via the SmartSimple platform, and it will be the unique entry point for all application submissions. Applications submitted by any other means will not be considered nor evaluated. Only the documentation in the right format included in the submission will be considered by evaluators. A full list of applicants will be drafted containing their basic information for statistical purposes and clarity (which will be also shared with the European Commission for transparency). The application reception will close on **21.04.2025, 17:00 CEST**. The deadline for submission is as stated in this Guidelines for Applicants document. Please note that the system time depends on the user's configured time zone and may or may not coincide with the correct time (this depends on the user, not the platform for submission).

Language

Applicants must submit their proposals in English. Submissions done in any other language will not be eligible and will not be evaluated. The grant management process (including the submission of documents and deliverables) will be conducted in English.

Ethical Issues

CoARA Boost strictly adheres to the fundamental ethical principles outlined in the "[European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#)." To ensure compliance, all applicants are required to acknowledge and accept our privacy policy and declaration of honour (ethics) during the submission process. This acknowledgment confirms that, by submitting the form, they accept the terms described in the provided text. No additional documents need to be uploaded; applicants are solely required to read and agree to the terms outlined when submitting the form. In terms of ethics, aligning project proposals with the principles of the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) is also strongly recommended.

During the evaluation process, the CoARA Secretariat may verify whether the self-assessment declaration aligns with the contents of the application. In cases where clarification is needed, the CoARA Secretariat reserves the right to contact the beneficiaries. If an applicant indicates that their application may have ethical issues, an ethics review will be conducted. Applications that fail to adequately address ethical concerns or privacy aspects will be rejected.

Data Protection

CoARA Boost Cascade Funding Call requires access to Personal and Entity Data to process and evaluate applications. As open call coordinator, ESF/CoARA

Secretariat will act as the Data Controller for all data submitted through the SmartSimple platform for this purpose. To ensure the safety and security of this data, the SmartSimple platform has been designed and operates under strict compliance with The General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR). Therefore, all applicants are required to accept the SmartSimple Platform terms to ensure full coverage. For more information regarding the data privacy policy and security measures implemented by SmartSimple, please refer to their [website](#).

Contact information

Any questions regarding the call can be directed to the CoARA Secretariat: funding@coara.org

In case of technical questions concerning the submission platform SmartSimple (operated by [ESF](#)) please reach out to: esf-panels@esf.org

An online information session for interested parties has been organised on the 30 of January 2025 at 14:00 CET, the materials presented during the session are available here: <https://zenodo.org/records/14794738>.

Support information

CoARA Secretariat offers a dedicated support channel available for applicants at funding@coara.org. Requests will receive a response within 2 working days of their submission. While all possible efforts will be made to respond in a timely manner, the applicants should plan their submissions, accordingly, allowing enough time before the deadline (i.e., at least 2 working days prior) if they expect an answer. Lack of the receipt of an answer to an enquiry shall not constitute grounds for extension or re-evaluation of a submission.

In addition to the support channels above, there is a collection of Frequently Asked Questions made available on the [website FAQ](#). This will be continuously updated from the questions received through the support channels.

Please note that any email received outside the designated support channel will not be taken into account. It is imperative that all requests or inquiries related to the submission system or the call itself are directed through the official support channels.

Technical Guidelines – Platform Guidelines for Applicants

For all correspondence concerning the online submission of your application, please send an email to esf-panels@esf.org.

REGISTER

If you have already registered on our platform, you will not need to do this step again. You can directly go to your portal (https://esf.smartsimple.ie/s_Login.jsp), login with your email address and the password you have selected and start your application.

You will be able to register on the submission platform using the following link:

https://esf.smartsimple.ie/s_signup.jsp?token=XVtQC1oGYV5ZSxtZXxJXR1JWYUIIH3Rt

Then, please fill in your Contact Information details. Required fields are marked with an asterisk “*”.

The screenshot shows the 'Platform Registration' page. At the top, there is a green header with the 'SCIENCE CONNECT' logo and the text 'Platform Registration'. Below this is a 'Contact Information' section. An 'Instructions' box states: 'Required fields are marked with an asterisk *'. Below the instructions, there is a paragraph: 'If you have already logged on to our platform to submit an application in the past with the same email address, please login to our platform https://esf.smartsimple.ie/s_Login.jsp. In any other case, please write to esf-panels@esf.org'. The form contains several fields: '* Title' (a dropdown menu), '* First Name' (a text input), '* Surname' (a text input), '* Email' (a text input), and '* Country' (a dropdown menu with '--- Select One ---'). At the bottom of the form, there is a checkbox for 'I'm not a robot' next to a reCAPTCHA logo and 'Privacy - Terms' link. A red arrow points to a green 'Submit' button at the bottom right of the form.

Once everything is completed, click on “Submit”. Then, click on “Login here”.

(!) Make sure that the email address you indicated is correct.

After a short while, you should receive a confirmation email, “Platform Registration confirmation”, from esf-panels@esf.org. If you have not received it in your inbox, **please check your spam folder.**

	de	objet	date	taille
	esf-panels@esf.org	*** SPAM *** Platform registration confi...	06/04/20 11:41	7.5 ko

In this email, you will find your login (the email address you have indicated on the Registration Form) and a temporary password to connect to the platform.

LOG IN TO THE PLATFORM

Once you have completed your first login (using the information provided in the email), you will have to choose a new password.

This is strictly personal and ESF will not have access to it.

(!) **Make sure to remember your password.**

You should then receive a verification code to enter the platform (please check spam and deleted items folders). You will then have access to your portal, your **profile** and your **application**.

First, you will need to complete your **profile**.

(!) **If your profile is not completed, you will not be able to submit your proposal.**

To complete your profile, click on the button “Click Here” on the “Welcome to your portal” section.

Fill in the Contact Information Details and click on “Complete Profile” once it is done.

Please note that once you have completed your profile, it will be locked and you will need to contact esf-panels@esf.org to modify it.

To go back to your portal, click on the arrow

SUBMIT YOUR APPLICATION

Click on “Apply” for the CoARA Boost 2024 Call.

Type	Call Name	Call Deadline Date	Action
Fight Kids Cancer	Fight Kids Cancer 2024 - Clinical Trial Full Applications	2024-02-15 15:00:00	The call deadline has passed.
Fight Kids Cancer	Fight Kids Cancer 2024 - Translational Research Full Applications	2024-02-15 15:00:00	The call deadline has passed.
Swiss Re Institute – AXA Research Fund	Joint Risk Resilience Partnership: Building Resilience against Systemic Cyber Risk 2023	2024-02-15 11:00:00	The call deadline has passed.
AgroServ TNA	AgroServ Transnational/Virtual Access 2024	2024-03-08 16:00:00	The call deadline has passed.
METU Programme	Enrich Together 2024	2024-04-16 13:00:00	Apply
CoARA Boost	CoARA Boost 2024	2024-06-17 16:00:00	Apply

Make sure that you do not hide the instructions.

You will have to dully fill in all the mandatory fields : Project Title, Type of project, Main and Second Keywords, Abstract, Contact details of the project coordinator, name and Organisation’s PIC number

Under **Template for Application & Instructions for Submission**, you will find these guidelines for the applicants, the Application template in word format that has to be used (mandatory) and to upload the PDF of your application once it is ready, click on the arrow as shown below:

* Upload PDF of Application

← View

Edit Application

* Project Number: 24-CoARA-002

* Project Title

* Type of project

--select one--

* Main keyword (please select one among the following)

--select one--

Second keyword (optional)

Please select up to two among the following.

- Assessment of research organisations
- Careers
- Assessment of research proposals
- Changing culture
- CVs and Narrative
- Disciplines and inter, trans and multidisciplinary
- Diversity
- Equity
- Ethics and integrity
- Impact
- Language
- Metrics and indicators
- Open Science

Save Draft Submit for review

(!) When you are filling in your application form, **remember to click on “Save Draft” regularly.**

The first time you will click on “Save Draft”, you will obtain the reference ID (project Number) for your application:

← View

Edit Application

* Project Number: 24-CoARA-002

* Project Title

* Type of project

--select one--

* Main keyword (please select one among the following)

--select one--

If you log out and re-login later, you will find your application under the “My Applications” section. You will have to click, then, on the Edit button.

Open Calls

Specified times correspond to the GMT zone (UK time).

External Open Calls

Type	Call Name	Call Deadline Date	Action
Fight Kids Cancer	Fight Kids Cancer 2024 - Clinical Trial Full Applications	2024-02-15 15:00:00	The call deadline has passed.
Fight Kids Cancer	Fight Kids Cancer 2024 - Translational Research Full Applications	2024-02-15 15:00:00	The call deadline has passed.
Swiss Re Institute – AXA Research Fund	Joint Risk Resilience Partnership: Building Resilience against Systemic Cyber Risk 2023	2024-02-15 11:00:00	The call deadline has passed.
AgroServ TNA	AgroServ Transnational/Virtual Access 2024	2024-03-08 16:00:00	The call deadline has passed.
METU Programme	Enrich Together 2024	2024-04-16 13:00:00	Apply
CoARA Boost	CoARA Boost 2024	2024-06-17 16:00:00	You have already created an application for this call.

My Applications and Rebuttals

APPLICATIONS (2) REBUTTALS (0) REBUTTALS MISSED DEADLINE (0)

#	Application Type	Project Number	Project Title	Call Name	Edit / View
1	CoARA Boost	24-CoARA-002		CoARA Boost 2024	Edit

Finally, when you are ready to submit your application, click on “Submit for review”. If you have made any modifications, you will need to first save them by clicking on “Save Draft” before submitting your application.

(!) Be careful, once you have submitted your application, you will not be able to modify it anymore!

Once you have submitted your application, the platform will generate a pdf overview of the fields you have completed that you can download by clicking on “Print Form”.

My Applications and Rebuttals

APPLICATIONS (2) REBUTTALS (0) REBUTTALS MISSED DEADLINE (0)

#	Application Type	Project Number	Project Title	Call Name	Edit / View
1	CoARA Boost	24-CoARA-002		CoARA Boost 2024	Print Form

If you need any help in submitting your application or using the submission platform, please contact esf-panels@esf.org.

4. Conclusion

In April 2024, the CoARA Secretariat within ESF launched the first round of the CoARA Boost Cascade Funding programme to support institutions in their efforts to implement commitments of the Agreement and reform research assessment practices within their organisations. The call was a success with 72 applications received from individual institutions within the European Research Area. The Call text and Applicants' Guidelines for Call 1 have been shared within D.5.1. "1st cascade funding competitive call text and guidelines for applicants" in May 2024.

25 projects have been selected and funded (they are introduced in D.5.4. "List of projects supported through the 1st Cascade Funding competitive call") within the 1st Call of the Cascade Funding programme to meet institutions at different stages in their reform journeys.

CoARA Boost 2nd Cascade Funding competitive call was launched in February 2025 with the aim to fund once again up to 25 projects fostering the Agreement and research assessment practices and tools. The same types of projects will be funded, within the same conditions. To inform CoARA communities and beyond about the call to be launched, an online information session was organised on the 30th of January 2025. To further support organisations interested in the call, another information session and brokerage event will take place on the 20th of March 2025. The 2nd round of selected projects will be introduced in D.5.7 "List of projects supported through the 2nd cascade funding competitive call" expected to be available in M21.

Finally, CoARA Boost Cascade Funding results and data generated are stored and made available publicly through D.5.6 "Cascade Funding Data Repository" which is expected to be updated according to the progress of the projects.

At the end of CoARA Boost, it is expected that the portfolio of funded projects will foster transformative development that will inform and inspire further change across the research community.